

« »

Natarova Elena Vladimirovna,
Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of Accounting, Analysis and Audit Department,
Institute of Economics and Management,
V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES AS A TOOL FOR PUBLIC FINANCE MANAGEMENT

Governments around the world strive to effectively manage public finances, following global trends and undergoing fundamental transformations in the way the public sector operates and delivers services to users. Consequently, government agencies at all levels are undergoing digital transformation to deliver public services more efficiently, transparently, and cost-effectively. Improved service quality is expected to contribute to increased government revenues and citizen satisfaction.

The development of digital technologies allows governments to interact with citizens and organizations through digital mechanisms. It also optimizes public finance management through the use of artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and storage, simplifying decision-making.

The digital transformation process is unique to each institution. Some organizations must implement highly complex digital processes, while others only need to implement basic digital processes. Digital transformation itself involves converting data into a digital format, which must then be stored, processed, and used using digital and information technologies. Digital transformation involves comprehensive changes in an institution's operations and leads to a new way of delivering services. Therefore, research into these issues is relevant.

The article's research methodology examines the digital transformation of public services as a tool for managing public finances globally and in Russia. The article examines the potential for digitalizing government activities based on the latest technological products; explores global experience in implementing government digitalization; and proposes a methodology for comprehensively assessing the digital readiness of institutions.

Keywords: digital transformation, government, assessment, tools.

[11], [14, 15], [15], [9], [12], [10], [13],

I.
2018–2024 .*

«

/	-	(.)							(. -)
		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	
1.	« - », :	220	290	290	300	250	250	250	1 850
1.1.		220	250	250	250	250	250	250	1 720
1.4.	-	—	40	40	50	—	—	—	130
2	« », :	439	10 533	22 056	32 434	23 196	24 322	30 650	143 631
2.1.		439	10 163	20 481	29 899	23 196	24 322	30 650	139 151
2.4.	-	—	370	1 575	2 535	—	—	—	4 480
3.	« - », :	1 496	17 501	18 156	22 870	25 950	29 800	14 700	130 473
3.1.		1 137	16 710	17 617	22 210	25 250	29 250	14 250	126 424
3.4.	-	359	791	539	660	700	550	450	4 049
4.	« », :	—	173 289	526 948	381 504	354 872	353 529	342 394	2 132 536
4.1.		445	78 073	117 824	131 204	104 872	103 529	92 394	628 341
4.4.	-	—	95 216	409 124	250 300	250 000	250 000	250 000	1 504 640
5.	« », :	364	7 403	9 533	9 315	1 050	979	773	29 417
5.1.		364	4 815	5 569	4 781	1 050	979	773	18 331
5.4.	-	—	2 588	3 964	4 534	—	—	—	11 086
6.	« - », :	4 762	26 188	43 966	47 484	38 293	37 600	39 554	237 847
6.1.		4 762	26 188	43 966	47 484	38 293	37 600	39 554	237 847
6.4.	-	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	-	7 726	235 204	620 949	493 907	443 611	446 480	428 321	2 676 198
	:	7 367	136 199	205 707	235 828	192 911	195 930	177 871	1 151 813
	:	359	99 005	415 242	258 079	250 700	250 550	250 450	1 524 385

* [16].

- « », -

» [7].

...

,

,

,

.

.

,

,

,

.

,

,

,

,

.

,

,

,

,

.

,

,

.

,

.

,

.

«

»,

.

,

,

:

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.
- 7.
- 8.

,

.

.

.

.

.

-

,

,

.

.

,

.

-

,

.

,

,

.

,

,

«
?

» [8]

)
)
)
)
)
)

?

?

?

?
?

?

?

?

)

?

)

?

)
)

?

?

?

)
)
)

,)?

(

)

?

)
)
)

? ?
?

?
,
?

- .

,
- , . ,
, , ,

)
)
)
)

- , :
- , ?
? ?
? ?
? ,

1. E-Government Survey 2024 Accelerating Digital Transformation for Sustainable Development With the addendum on Artificial Intelligence / Department of Economic and Social Affairs of United Nations. — URL: desapublications.un.org/publications/un-e-government-survey-2024 (date of the application: 10.11.2025).
2. 2020 . N 474. — URL: base.garant.ru/74404210/ (: 10.11.2025). 2030 : 21
3. 07.05.2024 N 309. — URL: www.consultant.ru/law/hotdocs/84648.html (: 10.11.2025). 2030 2036
4. 22 2021 . 2998- . — URL: static.government.ru/media/files/d3uclO4ZFGNKmxCPBXbL4OaMPALuGdQ.pdf (: 10.11.2025).
5. 16 2024 . 637- . — URL: static.government.ru/media/files/3VaEANLIFAKTxZgK8AI2XPBVtSPxw62e.pdf (: 10.11.2025).

6. URL: rk.gov.ru/articles/5f371140-b83c-46f4-a599-6ca2614a7b81 (: 10.11.2025).
7. URL: rk.gov.ru/articles/5f371140-b83c-46f4-a599-6ca2614a7b81 (: 10.11.2025).
8. URL: docs.cntd.ru/document/1200124394 (: 10.11.2025).
9. DOI 10.21681/1994-1404-2022-2-25-33. — EDN: DQLHIV.
10. URL: government.ru/news/41722/ (: 10.11.2025).
11. — 2023. — 1 (66). — 183-196. — EDN: SIHAXA.
12. — 2024. — 1 (62). — 161-171. — EDN: SIHAXA.
13. — 2024. — 2 (66). — 18-33. — EDN: MYFYXG.
14. — 2024. — 2 (66). — 34-44. — EDN: IVHRCV.
15. — 2023. — 1 (58). — 18-26. — EDN: TBGHHD.
16. «TAdviser. — 17 2024. — URL: www.tadviser.ru/index.php (: 10.11.2025).

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. E-Government Survey 2024 Accelerating Digital Transformation for Sustainable Development With the addendum on Artificial Intelligence / Department of Economic and Social Affairs of United Nations. — URL: desapublications.un.org/publications/un-e-government-survey-2024 (date of the application: 10.11.2025).
2. O natsii v tselyakh razvitiya Rossiyskoy Federatsii na period do 2030 goda: Ukaz Prezidenta RF ot 21 iyulya 2020 g. 474. — URL: base.garant.ru/74404210/ (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
3. O natsional'nom razvitiy Rossiyskoy Federatsii na period do 2030 goda i na perspektivu do 2036 goda: Ukaz Prezidenta RF ot 07.05.2024 N 309. — URL: www.consultant.ru/law/hotdocs/84648.html (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
4. Strategicheskoye napravleniye v oblasti tsifrovoy transformatsii gosudarstvennogo upravleniya: upravleniye rukovodstvom Rossiyskoy Federatsii ot 22 oktyabrya 2021 g. 2998-r. — URL: static.government.ru/media/files/d3uc1O4ZFGNKmxCPBXbL4OaMPALuGdQ.pdf (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
5. Strategicheskoye napravleniye v oblasti tsifrovoy transformatsii gosudarstvennogo upravleniya: upravleniye rukovodstvom Rossiyskoy Federatsii ot 16 marta 2024 g. 637-r. — URL: static.government.ru/media/files/3VaEANLIFAKTxZgK8AI2XPBVtSPxw62e.pdf (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
6. Strategiya v oblasti tsifrovoy transformatsii otrasley ekonomiki, sotsial'noy sfery i gosudarstvennogo upravleniya Respubliki Krym: postanovleniye Soveta Ministrov Respubliki Krym ot 20.08.2021 N 487. — URL: rk.gov.ru/articles/5f371140-b83c-46f4-a599-6ca2614a7b81 (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
7. V Respublike Krym provoditsya tsifrovaya transformatsiya vo vsehkh proyavleniyakh zhizni krymchan // Glavnoye upravleniye po realizatsii natsional'nykh proyektov (regional'nyy proyektnyy ofis). — URL: rk.gov.ru/articles/5f371140-b83c-46f4-a599-6ca2614a7b81 (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
8. Natsional'nyy standart sistemy Rossiyskoy federatsii menedzhmenta kachestva GOST R ISO 9001-2015: Prikaz Federal'nogo agentstva po tekhnicheskoy regulirovaniyu i metrologii ot 28 sentyabrya 2015 g. N 1391-st. — URL: docs.cntd.ru/document/1200124394 (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).
9. Smorchkova, L. N. Tsifrovoye pravitel'stvo kak perspektiva gosudarstvennogo upravleniya v Rossii: informatsionno-pravovyye aspekty / L. N. Smorchkova // Pravovaya informatika. — 2022 g. — 2. — S. 25-33. — DOI: 10.21681/1994-1404-2022-2-25-33. — EDN: DQLHIV.

10. Chernyshenko, D. Tsifrovaya platforma «Gosuslugi. Reshayem vmeste» budet zapushchena vo vsehkh sub»yektakh strany / D. Chernyshenko // Tsifrovoye pravitel'stvo. — . URL: government.ru/news/41722/ (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).

11. Kravchenko, L.A. Razvitiye biznesa v tsifrovoy ekosisteme: vozmozhnosti, riski i upravleniye / L.A. Kravchenko, I.A. Troyan // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2023. — 1 (66). — S. 183-196. — EDN: SIKHAKSA.

12. Shutayeva, Ye. A. Tsifrovizatsiya kak neobkhodimoye usloviye razvitiya vneshneekonomicheskoy deyatel'nosti regionov Rossii / Ye.A. Shutayeva, V.V. Pobirchenko // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2024. — 1 (62). — S. 161-171. — EDN: SIKHAKSA.

13. Butova, T. G. tsifrovyye tekhnologii dlya upravleniya ekonomicheskimi aktivami / T.G. Butova, D.D. Burkal'tseva, V.A. Kondrashin // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2024. — 2 (66). — S. 18-33. — EDN: MYFYXG.

14. Vorobyova, E. I. Primeneniye finansovykh metodov i tsifrovyykh finansovykh tekhnologiy v antikorrupcionnoy deyatel'nosti Rossiyskoy Federatsii / E. I. Vorobyova // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2024. — 2 (66). — S. 34-44. — EDN: IVHRCV.

15. Vorobyova, E. I. Tsifrovyye tekhnologii v finansovoy sfere: liderstvo ikh primeneniya v transformatsii ekonomiki Rossiyskoy Federatsii / E. I. Vorobyova, O. G. Blazhevich // Nauchnyy vestnik: finansy, banki, investitsii. — 2023. — 1 (58). — S. 18-26. — EDN: TBGHHD.

16. Finansirovaniye natsional'nogo proyekta Tsifrovaya ekonomika. Zhurnal «TAdviser. Gosudarstvo. Biznes. Tekhnologii. — Moskva. — 17 maya 2024. — URL: www.tadviser.ru/index.php (data obrashcheniya: 10.11.2025).

14 2025

2 2025